

The Bigger, the Better? Population Size and Satisfaction with Municipal Services

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Summary

- We examine whether citizens in larger municipalities tend to be more satisfied with municipal services in Norway over the 2010-2019 period.
 - We study this question by matching five survey waves collecting information on citizen satisfaction with a broad range of public services with information on the population size of Norwegian municipalities.
 - The results show that large population size is associated with *higher* satisfaction in some service areas (e.g., emergency medical services and public transportation), and *lower* satisfaction in other service areas (e.g., planning and building services).
 - Since 'optimal' jurisdiction size depends on the type of public service under consideration, inter-municipal cooperation(s) may be a more flexible tool (compared to amalgamations) to achieve the optimal size across multiple service areas.
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1. Introduction

Local governments often hold key responsibility for public services including primary education, social services, health- and elderly care, fire protection, municipal roads, environmental protection and waste disposal, as well as cultural services including local public libraries. A persistent question among both academic and policy audiences thereby relates to the optimal organization of such local public service provision. In this policy brief, we address one specific aspect of this overarching question: namely, the role of the size of local governments. That is, **we study whether it is better to provide local public services within the framework of large local political jurisdictions (possibly achieved via inter-municipal cooperation), or whether one should rather do so through local jurisdictions with a smaller population.** Unlike previous research, however, our outcome of interest is not given by objective, economic measures of government performance (such as cost efficiency). Rather, we are interested in how satisfied inhabitants are with local services, and how this is related to the population size of their local governments. **Citizen satisfaction is often considered a key indicator of (the perception of) government performance, which makes it a highly relevant measure to investigate.**

From a theoretical perspective, it is a priori unclear whether larger local jurisdictions will lead to higher or lower satisfaction with local public service

delivery. On the one hand, jurisdictions with a larger population size are often argued to be more cost-efficient in service production, administration and tax collection because they are able to achieve economies of scale (Tullock 1969; Mouritzen 1989; Blom-Hansen et al. 2016). As such, they may have a better basis for offering more and better services to citizens, which would be expected to lead to higher satisfaction. On the other hand, jurisdictions with a smaller population size tend to have a more homogeneous population and a smaller distance between politicians and the population, which makes it more likely that the implemented policies are more consistent with popular preferences (Oates 1972; Mouritzen 1989). This would lead to the expectation that citizen satisfaction with public services is higher under smaller local governments. Naturally, both arguments may play out to different extents depending on the type of service under consideration. There exist, after all, better opportunities for achieving economies of scale in cases where the demand for a service is high and its unit costs decrease considerably with production levels (such as in, for example, waste collection). The same may not be true for much more specialized services (such as childcare or healthcare services). As a result, it remains an **empirical question whether citizen satisfaction with public services increases or decreases with local population size.**

2. Data and Methodology

Our empirical analysis relies on two main data sources. The first is the Norwegian *Innbyggerundersøkelsen* (literally:

“Citizen survey”). This survey was first implemented in 2010 and then bi-annually since 2013 to measure Norwegians’ use of, and satisfaction with, public services at all levels of government. It collects detailed information at the individual level among a random selection of the Norwegian population, with response rates between 19% and 41% depending on the year ($N \approx 10.000$ respondents per year). **The key question of interest in our analysis is “How good or bad do you think the following public services are?” (measured on a seven-point scale).** We calculate the average citizen satisfaction with *local* public services in each Norwegian municipality in a given year. We do this separately for ten public services under the authority of local governments (i.e. childcare, primary education, General Practitioners, emergency care, hospital, health center, planning and building office, fire department, public transport, and library). The resulting ‘satisfaction’ score is our main dependent variable.

The second data source contains detailed information about all Norwegian municipalities over the period 1972-2019 (Fiva et al. 2019). This dataset includes information on the **municipalities’ population size (measured as the number of inhabitants on 1 January; our central independent variable)** as well as a number of additional characteristics we use as control variables in the analysis (such as age composition, unemployment rate, voter turnout, the number of parties competing in local elections, the seat share of left-wing parties in the local council, and total public expenditures). Both datasets are

combined using the year of observation and unique municipality codes.

Before we discuss our key findings, we should note that we estimate fixed effects regression models (to control for any unobservable municipality characteristics that do not change over time) and always include population size as well as its squared value as key independent variables. This first of all allows for a non-linear relation between municipality size and citizen satisfaction, which may be important. More importantly, however, this approach allows us to calculate the ‘optimal’ municipality size from our regression estimates for each public service included in our analysis. Consequently, our results can offer some insight into whether Norwegian municipalities are currently of an appropriate size *given* the level of satisfaction with specific public services among its citizenry.

3. Results

The results of our analysis are summarized in Table 1, which provides the findings for one local public service in each column. **A first observation from our analysis is that the level of satisfaction with specific public services is often unrelated to the size of the Norwegian municipalities providing these services.** This is at odds with a considerable part of the existing academic literature on the topic, and may be linked to our use of satisfaction as an outcome variable. Even though size may affect objective outcome measures including public sector efficiency, this need not translate into a similar relation for citizen

satisfaction (e.g., because the population does not *perceive* the objective differences accurately). Naturally, as mentioned above, it may also be that the relationship between size and satisfaction is specific to particular (types of) public services. There is some evidence of that in our main findings since we uncover three – out of ten – services where size does appear to matter.

On the one hand, we find a significant positive correlation between population size and satisfaction with emergency medical services and public transportation services: i.e. higher satisfaction in larger municipalities.

While emergency medical services can be considered as a service where unit costs decrease considerably with production levels (due to the very high fixed costs involved), public transportation services are a typical public service where a sufficient demand is required to achieve economies of scale. The optimal municipality size for these services is estimated at roughly 700.000 inhabitants, which is approximately the size of the Norwegian capital of Oslo. This is not necessarily an argument in favour of municipal mergers, particularly since citizen satisfaction is *not* linked to population size for most other services. Rather, it suggests that greater and stronger cooperation across municipal boundaries may be required for these types of services when the aim is to maximize citizen satisfaction with the service(s) provided.

Finally, and in sharp contrast, **we observe a significant negative correlation for planning and building services: i.e. lower satisfaction in larger**

municipalities. In this case the *worst* possible municipal size is estimated to lie around 600.000 inhabitants. One likely reason for this result is that planning and building services – such as urban design, land use development, lift inspections, and granting building permissions – require detailed knowledge of the local situation. They also generally involve the same set of formal and legal steps (e.g., environmental impact analyses) that are specific to each individual decision. This makes it a highly specialized service that is difficult to ‘scale up’, such that smaller jurisdiction size may become ideal when the aim is to maximize citizen satisfaction with the service(s) provided.

4. Conclusion

Overall, our findings highlight that citizen satisfaction with local public service provision is on the whole rarely related to the size of local jurisdictions. In our Norwegian setting over the time period 2010-2019, this is the case for seven out of ten public services. Furthermore, when there is a correlation between satisfaction and jurisdiction size, the positive or negative direction of this relationship depends on the service at hand. Taken together, these observations strongly indicate that the ‘optimal’ jurisdiction size for the provision of local public services depends on the type of public service under consideration. **We thus suggest that, as a general rule, inter-municipal cooperation(s) may constitute a more flexible tool (compared to municipal amalgamations) to achieve the optimal size across multiple service areas at the same time.** After all, targeted cooperation can be restricted to specific public service

areas. Municipal mergers, however, by construction create a uniform (larger) size for all public service areas at once, which may be hard to ‘downsize’ for specific services that benefit from a smaller scale of service provision.

Naturally, our analysis comes with some caveats and limitations that should be taken into account while interpreting our findings. First, our results may depend on how satisfaction is measured, as well as on the specific characteristics of Norwegian municipalities and their overarching institutional setting. Further analyses in other settings and using alternative measures of satisfaction thus would be essential to verify the robustness and general nature of our inferences. Furthermore, our empirical approach cannot rule out that there may be an issue of simultaneous causation where a drop in (within-municipality) population size is the result of low levels of user satisfaction. This can be the case, for instance, when citizens ‘vote with their feet’ and relocate to another jurisdiction if service provision is unsatisfactory (Tiebout 1956; Banzhaf and Walsh 2008). Future research exploiting exogenous shocks to population sizes may constitute one route to address this important issue.

What is DemoTrans ?

DemoTrans is an impact-driven research project that will provide theoretically and empirically robust recommendations on how to reinvigorate democratic governance by improving the accountability, transparency, effectiveness and trustworthiness of rule-of-law based institutions and policies.

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Further Information:

- Bogen, Øivind Johnsen (2022). *Kommunestørrelse og tilfredshet med kommunale tjenester: En kvantitativ studie av innbyggernes tilfredshet med kommunale tjenester i perioden 2010 – 2019*. Unpublished Master thesis, University of Bergen. <https://bora.uib.no/bora-xmlui/handle/11250/3001151>.

Table 1: Main results

	Child care	Primary education	General Practitioner	Emergency care	Hospital	Health center	Planning office	Fire department	Public transport	Library
Pop	0.006 (0.012)	0.012 (0.012)	0.007 (0.015)	0.072*** (0.019)	0.0001 (0.014)	-0.010 (0.023)	-0.031* (0.017)	-0.007 (0.012)	0.043** (0.018)	-0.004 (0.013)
Pop ²	-0.000 (0.000)	-0.000 (0.000)	-0.000 (0.000)	-0.000*** (0.000)	0.000 (0.000)	0.000 (0.000)	0.000** (0.000)	0.000 (0.000)	-0.000*** (0.000)	0.000 (0.000)
Controls	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
N	1951	1958	1977	1965	1954	1535	1914	1951	1966	1960

Note: The table reports the coefficient estimates of fixed effects regression models with average citizen satisfaction a given public service as the dependent variable and population size (and its squared value) as the main independent variables. All models includes a full set of municipality fixed effects and controls for municipality characteristics that change over time (see main text). Standard errors in parentheses; *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

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